

Mapping Nighttime Food Deserts in London

Michał Iliev^{*1}, James Cheshire^{†1} and Stephen Law^{‡1}

¹Department of Geography, UCL

GISRUK 2025

Summary

Approximately 1.32 million Londoners work in the evening and nighttime economy, yet their workplace distribution, commuting patterns, and access to amenities remain understudied. This study addresses this gap by analysing nighttime workers' access to healthy and affordable food, a concern for 52% of surveyed workers. Using a dynamic accessibility model, it integrates worker footfall counts from mobile phone location data, variability in transportation, and opening hours of shops to capture spatial and temporal variations in food accessibility between 6 pm and 6 am. Additionally, we introduce a framework to aid policymakers identify areas with inadequate food accessibility for nighttime workers.

KEYWORDS: night workers, spatial accessibility, spatial justice, food deserts, policy

1. Introduction and Background

Approximately a quarter of London's workforce (roughly 1.32 million people) falls under the definition of a nighttime worker – an individual who typically works between 6 pm and 6 am (GLA Economics, 2024). Despite the establishment of the Night Time Commission in 2016 and the 24-hour vision for London in 2017 by the Greater London Authority (GLA), research on the workplace distribution, commuting patterns, and amenities available to nighttime workers remains limited. Moreover, existing policies predominantly focus on the commercial aspects of the night-time economy (NTE), often overlooking the challenges faced by the very workers who sustain it (McArthur et al., 2019; Acuto et al., 2022). One such challenge is access to healthy and affordable food: 52% of 2,142 nighttime workers surveyed by the Living Wage Foundation reported difficulty accessing healthy food during night shifts, with 35% stating that 24-hour access to such options would improve their working conditions (Cottell, 2024). Better research on how access to food varies spatially and temporally is therefore crucial for policymakers to support Londoners working at night.

Although food deserts are the product of various factors (e.g., quality and price of food), physical access to food outlets is the central issue. While the causal link between living in a food desert and poor diet-related health outcomes is debated, spatial (in)justice remains a pressing issue for those without adequate access to healthy and affordable food (Smith, 2023). Everyone should have the capability to make healthy dietary choices, regardless of income, ethnicity, or home/work location. Although food deserts are a widely researched topic in the UK (see Smith & Thompson, 2023, for the overview), most research has focused on residential areas during a single daytime hour, providing only a static perspective. This paper aims to address this gap by applying a dynamic location-based accessibility model, introduced by Järv et al. (2018), to **nighttime workers in London**. By integrating three temporal layers – the spatial distribution of night workers (derived from mobile phone location data), transportation (walking + public transportation), and opening hours of grocery stores – the model captures hourly changes in food accessibility between 6 pm and 6 am using a granular hexagonal grid.

* michal.iliev@ucl.ac.uk

† james.cheshire@ucl.ac.uk

‡ stephen.law@ucl.ac.uk

As part of an ongoing collaboration between UCL and the GLA, this study aims to produce policy-relevant insights that identify areas with high nighttime working activity, but with limited food access. The final phase involves developing simple heuristics, guided by the principle of “sufficientarianism”, to assist policymakers in prioritising interventions in underserved areas (Martens, 2017). The findings are anticipated to be particularly relevant for workers outside the public sector, a group that is often less institutionally supported and more likely to lack access to alternative food sources such as canteens.

2. Data

This preliminary analysis is done for a single Friday/Saturday night (1–2 March 2024). The dynamic accessibility model consists of three key layers. Each change as a function of time and are set out below.

People layer (spatial distribution of night workers): anonymised and aggregated footfall counts derived from BT’s Geolocated Mobile Network Data (GeoMND), accessed via the High Streets Data Service. The data are collected by continuously tracking all devices on the network (30% of the market share), using signal triangulation. Before aggregation, the data was scaled to the UK population by comparing inferred home locations against census demographic data, ensuring the counts approximate actual footfall rather than that of BT users alone. To validate the data, BT compared its footfall counts to official match-day attendance figures at two London football stadiums, finding discrepancies of only 0.3% and 4.6%, respectively.ⁱ Footfall data are provided for 15,041 hexagons (350m edge-to-edge) covering the Greater London area, with the entire analysis conducted at this hexagonal level. Footfall counts represent the number of people who stayed within a given hexagon for at least 10 minutes during a defined 3-hour time-window (e.g., midnight to 3 am). Home and work locations are inferred based on the most and second-most frequently visited locations of each person, allowing for categorisation of counts into residents, workers, and visitors. This study focuses specifically on worker counts during evening and nighttime hours (6-9pm, 9pm-midnight, midnight-3am, 3-6am). For the model, we calculate the proportion of workers captured in each hexagon during each time-window.

Transportation layer: public transport schedule data in General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) format. Two GTFS files were utilised: one containing Transport for London (TfL) services and the other covering rail services.ⁱⁱ

Activity locations layer: the location and opening hours of grocery stores provided by the Local Data Company (LDC) via the SDRUK Geographic Data Service.ⁱⁱⁱ The data is physically verified and regularly updated. Since the study aims to calculate accessibility to places selling affordable and healthy food, it follows Tenkanen et al. (2016) by including shops that offer a selection of fruits, vegetables, and dairy products. Based on these criteria, four LDC subcategories were selected: ‘Supermarkets’, ‘Grocers’, ‘Greengrocers & Fruitsellers’, and ‘Convenience Stores’. Moreover, to account for the boundary effect, we include stores up to 2000 meters from the city’s borders (N=8,337).

3. Methodology

We measure accessibility as travel-time between origins (locations of night workers) and destinations (open grocery stores) for each hour between 6 pm and 6 am. For details on the dynamic location-based accessibility model, see Järv et al. (2018).

The first step involves calculating a travel-time matrix between the centroids of all hexagons in the study area (including a buffer zone) for each departure time. This is done using *r5r*, an R package for rapid realistic routing on multimodal transport networks, which incorporates GTFS and street networks data (Pereira et al., 2021). Door-to-door travel-times account for all components of the journey,

ⁱ Details regarding the data are drawn from internal documentation provided by BT Active Intelligence.

ⁱⁱ TfL data via BODS: <https://data.bus-data.dft.gov.uk/>; Rail data: <https://opendata.nationalrail.co.uk/>.

ⁱⁱⁱ <https://data.cdrc.ac.uk/dataset/local-data-company-retail-type-vacancy-and-address-data>

including walking, waiting, and transfer times. If walking is faster than using public transportation to reach the destination, which is often the case at night, the walking time is used. For each departure time, travel-time is calculated for every minute within a 30-minute window, with the median value reported. Full details on the parameters are available in Table 2 of the Supplementary Materials.

The second step links the travel-time matrices with the activities layer. Using the *r5r* outputs and the *R accessibility* package, travel-times (in minutes) are calculated to the nearest hexagon containing at least one open food store for each departure time. This process generates one travel-time result per hexagon for each hour (12 in total). It is important to note that if, for example, a store closes at 9 pm, it is considered within the pool for an 8 pm departure but excluded for a 9 pm departure.

Finally, the share of workers within each hexagon during a given time-window is linked to the accessibility results. This combined dataset enables analysis of the proportion of nighttime workers with access to an open food store within specified travel-time thresholds across the night. As the BT data is provided in 3-hour time-windows, it is assumed that the share of workers remains constant within these intervals. It should also be noted that the total number of workers differs across time-windows, meaning the shares do not correspond to identical absolute values.

To support policymakers, this study also develops a framework for the straightforward identification of areas of concern. While numerous studies and policies advocate for the clear definition of what constitutes "sufficient" access to a given opportunity (van der Veen et al., 2020), the GLA currently lacks a standardised threshold for food accessibility. In this preliminary analysis, we adopt a 10-minute travel-time threshold; however, this parameter can be adjusted to align with the specific needs of individual boroughs. Using this threshold, we identify areas with nighttime workers that fail to meet the accessibility standard for each hour. Given that policies related to the NTE are often implemented at the borough level, this paper presents exemplary results using Greenwich as a case study.

4. Results

4.1. Travel-time to the closest open grocery store

The outputs of the accessibility analysis, which account for transport system supply and availability of shops at different hours of the day, illustrate how travel-time to the nearest open grocery store varies spatially and temporally. Results were selected for four representative departure times: 6 pm, 10 pm, 11 pm, and 5 am (Fig. 1).

Between 6 pm and 10 pm, the accessibility levels across London are very high, with over 90% of hexagons having an open shop within a 10-minute walk/PT journey. Certain green areas, such as Richmond Park, and locations near the city border exhibit poorer accessibility, even when accounting for stores within a 2 km buffer. Still, travel-times remain under 30 minutes for most of these areas. By 11 pm, accessibility levels decrease, with only 75% of hexagons maintaining access within 10 minutes, and this drops further to below 70% by midnight. While central London continues to exhibit high accessibility to food services at night, travel times in outer boroughs increase significantly, underscoring the greater challenges faced by nighttime workers (and residents) in these areas.

4.2. Modelling dynamic accessibility

The travel-time results illustrate the spatial (in)accessibility to grocery stores but do not account for the number of individuals affected (i.e., the demand). Figure 2 presents the outcomes of the dynamic accessibility model, which considers the spatial distribution of workers over time. Between 6 pm and 10 pm, over 90% of workers can access the nearest store within 10 minutes. However, this proportion decreases to approximately 65% at midnight and 58% at 2 am. These findings underscore the importance of incorporating temporality into accessibility studies, as a static model would fail to capture these disparities and the associated challenges.

Figure 1 Spatial variation of travel-times to the closest grocery store at four chosen hours. The results for all 12 departure times are presented in the Supplementary Materials.

Figure 2 Dynamic accessibility model results. Lines indicate the share of workers that can access the closest grocery store within a given travel-time, broken down by hour of the day. The horizontal dashed line marks the 10-minute threshold.

4.3. Policy context: meeting accessibility threshold in Greenwich

The BT data recorded the following number of workers in Greenwich during the selected evening and nighttime period (Table 1).

Table 1 Count of workers in Greenwich recorded in BT footfall data (1–2 March 2024).

Time-window	Number of workers
6 pm – 9 pm	21,220
9 pm – 12 am	13,797
12 am – 3 am	8,804
3 am – 6 am	7,913

Figure 3 illustrates the proportion of Greenwich workers who can access a grocery store within a given travel-time for each hour. Between 6 pm and 9 pm, over 90% of workers can reach a grocery store within a 10-minute walk or PT journey. However, this rate declines sharply with each hour, dropping to below 40% after midnight. These findings contrast with citywide results, underscoring the importance of analysing accessibility at a local level. Furthermore, the maps in Figure 4 depict areas where (1) nighttime workers were detected, but (2) there is no grocery store within 10-minutes for four selected hours. The number of workers within hexagons that fall below this threshold offers valuable insights for policymakers. Future work will focus on enhancing the framework to identify hotspots of underserved areas more effectively.

Figure 3 Dynamic accessibility model results for Greenwich. Lines indicate the share of workers that can access the closest grocery store within a given travel-time, broken down by hour of the day. The horizontal dashed line marks the 10-minute threshold.

Figure 4 Number of workers recorded in BT footfall data. The count is presented only for areas that do not meet the accessibility threshold (no grocery store within a 10-minute journey). Grey areas represent hexagons that meet the threshold and/or where no workers were detected.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

The indicators presented in this study are not absolute truths, as several factors have been simplified or excluded. For example:

- Variations in price and quality of products across stores are not accounted for.
- The analysis considers only the closest shop, disregarding personal preferences, capacity and number of shops within a given threshold.
- The selection of a 10-minute threshold is not explicitly supported by health geography research.
- Due to the disclosure control applied to BT data, counts below 10 are treated as missing, resulting in the exclusion of some night workers from the analysis.

Despite these limitations, the study represents a significant step forward by shifting the focus of location-based accessibility research from residential to workplace contexts, a perspective rarely explored. Additionally, it is arguably the first accessibility study that explicitly considers the spatial distribution of workers within the model. Finally, the research highlights the variability in nighttime accessibility, an aspect often overlooked in London studies. Future research will aim to develop an interactive dashboard to facilitate the practical application of these results by local authorities and borough organisations.

6. Acknowledgements

This research is co-funded by: the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC) via UBEL DTP and GHD; the Mayor of London; and UCL Knowledge Exchange. The data for this research have been provided by: the Geographic Data Service, a Smart Data Research UK Investment, under project ID GeoDS 1752, ES/Z504464/1; Greater London Authority High Streets Data Service.

References

- Acuto M., Seijas A, McArthur J, and Robin E (2022). *Managing Cities at Night: A Practitioner Guide to the Urban Governance of the Night-Time Economy, 1st ed.* Bristol University Press, Bristol.
- Cottell J (2024). London After Dark: The Reality of Working at Night in the Capital. Available at: <https://www.livingwage.org.uk/london-after-dark-reality-working-night-capital> (Accessed: 10 December 2024).
- GLA Economics (2024). London at Night: An Updated Evidence Base for a 24 Hour City. Available at: <https://data.london.gov.uk/download/london-at-night--research-and-analysis/5311efaa-47c8-4664-a188-09e8763ae678/London-at-Night-Update-2024%20%28FOR%20PDF%29.pdf> (Accessed: 22 January 2025).
- Järv O, Tenkanen H, Salonen M, Ahas R and Toivonen T (2018). Dynamic cities: Location-based accessibility modelling as a function of time. *Applied Geography*, 95, 101-110.
- Martens K (2017). *Transport justice: designing fair transportation systems*. Routledge, New York.
- McArthur J, Robin E, Smeds E (2019). Socio-spatial and temporal dimensions of transport equity for London's night time economy. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 121, 433-443.
- Pereira R H M, Saraiva M, Herszenhut D, Braga C K V and Conway M W (2021). R5r: Rapid realistic routing on multimodal transport networks with R5 in R. *Findings*.
- Smith D (2023). *Food deserts* in Smith D and Thompson C (eds.) *Food Deserts and Food Insecurity in the UK: Exploring Social Inequality*. Routledge, Abingdon, 8-23.
- Smith D and Thompson C (2023). *Food Deserts and Food Insecurity in the UK: Exploring Social Inequality*. Routledge, Abingdon.
- Tenkanen H, Saarsalmi P, Järv O, Salonen M and Toivonen T (2016). Health research needs more comprehensive accessibility measures: Integrating time and transport modes from open data. *International Journal of Health Geographics*, 15, 1.
- van der Veen A S, Annema J A, Martens K, van Arem B and Correia G H de A (2020). Operationalizing an indicator of sufficient accessibility – a case study for the city of Rotterdam. *Case studies on transport policy*, 8(4), 1360-1370.

Supplementary Material

Table 2 Inputs in the travel-time matrix calculation using r5r

Parameter	Selected value/inputs
origins	centroids of 14,664 hexagons (original BT grid – inaccessible hexagons, which do not have any street network within itself)
destinations	centroids of 18,481 hexagons (origins cells + hexagons within 2000-meter buffer around Greater London)
mode	WALK and TRANSIT
departure_datetime	12 different departure hours (6pm – 5am)
max_trip_duration	60 minutes
time_window	30 minutes
walk_speed	5 (km/h)
percentiles	50 th (median)

Figure 5 Travel-times to the closest open grocery store between 6 pm and 6 am.

Biographies

Michał Iliev is a PhD student in the UCL Department of Geography, specialising in the topics of urban mobility and accessibility. His doctoral research leverages existing datasets and methodologies to quantitatively analyse urban dynamics during nighttime, providing insights into how cities function after dark.

James Cheshire is Professor of Geographic Information and Cartography at UCL, Director of the UCL Social Data Institute and Deputy Director of the SDRUK Geographic Data Service.

Dr. Stephen Law is currently a lecturer (Assistant Professor) in Social and Geographic Data Science in UCL Geography. His research focuses principally on geographic data science, urban image analysis urban economics, urban design and space syntax.